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Efficiency improvements for the Generalized Sturmian method on scattering problems

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Synopsis Three aspects of the Generalized Sturmian Function method are discussed, adding to the flexibility of the formulation.

Generalized Sturmian (GS) basis sets have by now been proven to be useful tools in the solution of many atomic physics problems by an ab-initio formulation (see [1], [2] and references therein). They are generated from the following equation:

$[T_l + U(r) - E_{st}] S_{l,n}(r) = -\beta_n V(r) S_{l,n}(r)$, where T_l is the radial kinetic energy, $V(r)$ is the generating potential, and $U(r)$ the auxiliary one. The asymptotic behavior of the whole set is shaped by the boundary condition, the energy E_{st} and the auxiliary potential, which may contain a coulombic tail. In this work we are considering outgoing wave type behavior. To test the versatility of the basis set we consider the solution of the following driven equation

$$[T_l + V_L(r) - E] \psi_{sc}(r) = -V_R(r) \phi(r). \quad (1)$$

This type of equation appear on two-particle scattering problems, three-body problem on high energy regime and also on single photoionization of atoms.

Under the GS approach, the solution $\psi_{sc}(r)$ of this problem can be expressed as follows:

$$\psi_{sc}(r) = \sum_n a_n S_{l,n}(r). \quad (2)$$

The conventional procedure is then to project both sides of (1) onto each GS element and then solve the resulting linear system of equations for the coefficients a_n [3].

The goal of this communication is to introduce and discuss a simple set of ideas aimed to enhance the capabilities of the GS method to address scattering problems. We are going to analyze three aspects:

I) The expansion of the RHS of (1) with the introduction of an expansion potential $V_E(r)$:

The idea behind this procedure is to aid the

basis in the proper extraction of the RHS information. The RHS is expanded in a general way

$$V_R(r) \phi(r) = \sum_n b_n V_E(r) S_{l,n}(r). \quad (3)$$

Then we project onto each basis element and solve a linear system for the b_n coefficients. The potential $V_E(r)$ can be chosen to be equal to $V_R(r)$ or even to $V(r)$, but it does not necessarily have to be so.

II) Decaying/nondecaying RHS and generating potential range:

Localized and spread-out generating potentials $V(r)$ and their resulting Sturmian sets are compared. We expose to which problems is either one better suited.

III) Making one basis set work for many different energies:

Photoionization calculations require resolutions with many different ionization energies. The basis set is required to expand the solution in a wider radial domain, even in the asymptotic region, since its energy E_{st} will no longer equal the ejection energy E . Care must be taken while evaluating the overlapping integrals of two basis elements. The integration has to be analytically extended up to infinity, employing the knowledge of their asymptotic behavior.

Different scattering problems will be solved and all of them compared with independent finite difference calculations.

References

- [1] A. L. Frapiccini *et al* 2010 *J.Phys. B* **43** 101001
- [2] J. M. Randazzo *et al* 2011 *Phys. Rev. A* **84**, 052715.
- [3] M. J. Ambrosio *et al* 2012 *J. Phys. A* **45** 015201.

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